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ASTANGA YOGA: A RATIONALE FOR PREVENTING & TREATING NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES – A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Background: According to Yoga Vashishtha, an ancient yogic text, explains that disease (vyadhi) can be broadly classified into two categories, Adhija vyadhi (caused by internal causes that is due to the imbalances and disharmony in the Manomaya and Pranamaya koshas) and Anadhija vyadhi (caused by an internal cause like accidents, infections, etc). In adhija vyadhi (stress-induced disorders or noncommunicable diseases), lifestyle changes play a major role in treating patients. The most important component of changing lifestyle is “changing the mind of an individual” because everyone knows what is to be done and what lifestyle needs to be followed, but it is the most difficult thing to be achieved.

Materials and methods: We know according to Yoga Therapy, NCDs cause speeding up and constriction of the manomaya kosha. Astanga yoga can be used as a rationale to manage and correct the manomaya kosha. Once the mind is controlled, everything will become all right. So the main approach should be to relax and expand the manomaya kosha. This can be achieved by the practice of Astanga yoga

Yama niyama asana pranayama pratyahara dharana dhyana samadhyah astau angani”

- PYS chapter – 2 sloka no:29

Discussion: Asana and saucha – helpful in correcting the disturbances in annamaya kosha. Pranayama – helpful in correcting the disturbances in pranamaya kosha. Santhosha, ishwara pranidhanani, pratyahara, Yama, Dharana, and Dhyana help to correct the manomaya kosha, swadhyaya, and Dhyana helps to correct the vigjnanamaya kosha. Samadhi helps for reaching anandamaya kosha

Conclusion: ashtanga yoga will be used as a rationale to prevent and treat non-communicable diseases.

Keywords: Non-communicable diseases, ashtanga yoga, lifestyle, mind, vyadhi

Introduction:

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are defined as long-term diseases and generally slow in progression (1). But despite being "non-communicable", the global incidence of NCDs is on the rise, placing a huge burden on both nations and on individuals (2). The cost of treatment of NCDs is almost double that of other diseases and conditions(1). Since NCDs affect people in their most productive years (30-70 years), their effect can be felt by both the individual in the form of ill-health and economic cost, and by the society which has to bear the costs of loss in productivity and provide healthcare. NCDs have been labeled as Idiopathic which means "a condition that arises spontaneously or for which the cause is unknown" (3). Without knowing the cause what are they treating then? What is treated is only the symptom of the disease, but not its roots; what is achieved is just the symptomatic relief, not the cure, previous incidences of NCDs are not cured; and on the other hand, the number of new incidences of NCDs is increasing every year (4). In relation to NCDs, the Healthcare system has thereby turned into a Disease-care system. Diseases are maintained lifelong, but health is not restored. As urgent as the need to find effective cures for NCDs, equally urgent is the need to develop strategies to prevent them. This requires a proper understanding of these diseases and their origins. After looking in vain for the cause of disease in the body, the focus has gradually shifted to the mind as the source of both mental and physical diseases. Thus, the holistic approach to treating diseases is showing increasingly positive results to deal with NCDs.

The factors that cause the development of an NCD can be broadly categorized into two types:

- 1) Wrong lifestyle
- 2) Stress.

A wrong lifestyle includes a sedentary work routine, lack of physical exercise, wrong food habits (binge eating, junk eating, irregular timings), unhealthy habits such as smoking and alcohol, lack of exposure to nature, etc. Even if these issues have not been tackled on a large scale yet, there is at least a general awareness about them; these are well accepted as the cause of health disorders, and therefore do not need to be preached on. But stress is a new player on the field.

Stress has been found to contribute to diseases like diabetes (Pouwer, F., Kupper, N. and Adriaanse, M. (2010)), cardiovascular disease (6), obesity (Bose et al., 2009), etc. Ongoing

research is finding that "perseverative cognition" (i.e. repetitive thinking in the form of worry, rumination, etc.) is also linked to diseases (8).

Moreover, stress leads to poor lifestyle choices (people eat more, or smoke/drink to handle stress), and therefore the situation becomes vicious. As a result, NCDs affecting people later in their life (say, the 70s) until a few decades ago, have now been gradually dragged down to as low as the 30s or even 20s (9).

Fig:1- Stress-induced bodily reactions and factors involved (10)

It is not in our nature to accept accountability for our problems. People do not accept very easily that it is their lifestyle and their stressful way of reacting to the world that caused their disease. In that attempt, heredity becomes a convenient excuse. The discovery of DNA

effectively explained the transmission of genetic information across generations. Someone must have commenced that deformation in his genetic expressions through a poor lifestyle (11). Several studies in the last decade or so have revealed that we can very well regulate our genetic expressions. Even if a particular genetic expression (pertaining to disease) is stronger in us due to heredity, it can be weakened and switched off if we do the right things and adopt a healthy lifestyle (12).

After the connection between many of the NCDs and stress became evident, the name "Psychosomatic diseases" (PSD) has come into usage. Here, *psycho* means mind, and *soma* means body; thus PSD refers to a disease whose symptoms are at the physical level but rooted at the mental level (i.e. stress) (13). When you think the coupling of "stress" and "disease" into PSD is a purely modern phenomenon, you are in for a great surprise; because exactly the same term appears in ancient Indian texts such as Yoga Vasistha as "Adhija vyadhi" which translates into "bodily disease (Vyadhi) born out of (ja) mental unrest (Adhi) (14). According to yoga vasistha, there are two causes for sorrow 1. Adhi 2. Vyadhi. Sometimes they arise together, sometimes they cause each other, and sometimes they follow (independently of) each other. Vyadhi is nothing but physical stress and Adhi is a form of mental distress. Both are rooted in ignorance (Avidhya). They end when knowledge of the truth (i.e. self-knowledge) is attained (14).

Fig -2: How Adhi leads to Vyadhi (15)

Among the vyadhi, there are two major classifications of disease. Those that are caused by the mind are primary (adhija vyadhi, the psychosomatic, stress disorders) while those that afflict the body directly are secondary (anadhija vyadhi, infectious disease, accidents, etc). The primary disease has two subdivisions. These are the samanya (ordinary physical diseases) and

the Sara (the essential disorder of rebirth that may only be destroyed by atma jnana or knowledge of the Divine Self). Samanya diseases are the ones that affect us physically and may be destroyed by the correction of the mind-body disharmony. It is in these psychosomatic disorders that the actual practical application of Yoga practices as a mode of therapy can be very useful (14).

Fig:3 – classification of disease (vyadhi) according to yoga vaisista (15)

In adhija vyadhi (stress-induced disorders or noncommunicable diseases), lifestyle changes play a major role in treating patients. The most important component of changing lifestyle is “changing the mind of an individual” because everyone knows what is to be done and what lifestyle needs to be followed, but it is the most difficult thing to be achieved.

Materials and methods:

We know according to Yoga Therapy, NCDs cause speeding up and constriction of the manomaya kosha. Astanga yoga (the 8 limbs of yoga) given by the sage Patanjali, can be used as a rationale to manage and correct the manomaya kosha.

Yama niyama asana pranayama pratyahara dharana dhyana samadhayah astau angani
 - PYS chapter – 2 sloka no:29 (16)

1. **YAMA**- The Yama are five ethical precepts that outline a code of conduct that should be observed when interacting with the world around us (social ethics). They offer guidance on how to act toward others. They are: I. Ahimsa (Non-Violence) II. Satya (Truthfulness) III. Asteya (Non-Stealing) IV. Brahmacharya (Celibacy) V. Aparigraha (Non-Coveting)
2. **NIYAMA** - The Niyama are five ethical precepts that are inward

practices to improve the self (personal ethics). They are: I. Saucha (Purification) II. Santosa (Contentment) III. Tapas (Asceticism) IV. Svadhyaya (Study) V. Ishvara Pranidhana (Dedication to God/Master) 3. **Asanas** - Yoga postures or postures. 4. **Pranayamas** - Proper regulation of life force (Prana) through certain breathing techniques. 5. **Pratayahara** - Taking the senses inwards. 6. **Dharana** - One-pointed focus. 7. **Dhyana** – Meditation. 8. **Samadhi** - the highest state of consciousness (16).

Discussion: Yoga may be considered the original mind-body medicine. Yogic concepts and techniques enable the development of the right attitudes towards life and enable us to correct the numerous internal and external imbalances we suffer due to our wrong lifestyle/ genetic potential. Yoga enables us to take responsibility for our own health and happiness (15). From the Yogic viewpoint of disease, it can be seen that psychosomatic, stress-related disorders appear to progress through four distinct phases. These can be understood as follows:

1. Psychic Phase: This phase is marked by mild but persistent psychological and behavioral symptoms of stress like irritability, disturbed sleep, and other minor symptoms. This phase can be correlated with manomaya koshas. Yoga as a mind-body therapy is very effective in this phase.

2. Psychosomatic Phase: If the stress continues there is an increase in symptoms, along with the appearance of generalized physiological symptoms such as occasional hypertension and tremors. This phase can be correlated with manomaya and pranamaya koshas. Yoga as a mind-body therapy is very effective in this phase.

3. Somatic Phase: This phase is marked by disturbed function of organs, particularly the target, or involved organ. At this stage, one begins to identify the diseased state. This phase can be correlated with pranamaya and annamaya koshas. Yoga as a therapy is less effective in this phase and may need to be used in conjunction with other methods of treatment.

4. Organic Phase: This phase is marked by full manifestation of the diseased state, with pathological changes such as an ulcerated stomach or chronic hypertension, becoming manifest in their totality with their resultant complications. This phase can be correlated with the annamaya kosha as the disease has become fixed in the physical body. Yoga as a therapy has a palliative and ‘quality of life improving’ effect in this phase. It also has positive emotional and psychological effects even in terminal and end-of-life situations (15).

Once the mind is controlled, everything will become all right. So, the main approach should be to relax and expand the manomaya kosha. This can be achieved by the practice of Astanga yoga.

Practices of ashtanga yoga according to the IAYT protocol:

Asana, brahmacharya, and saucha – helpful in correcting the disturbances in annamaya kosha.

Pranayama – helpful in correcting the disturbances in pranamaya kosha.

Santhosha, ishwara pranidhanani, pratyahara, Yama, Dharana, and Dhyana - help to correct disturbances in manomaya kosha,

swadhyaya, and Dhyana - helps to correct the vigjnanamaya kosha.

Samadhi - helps in reaching anandamaya kosha

By the regular practice of yoga, there is a significant increase in the vagal tone, a decrease in sympathetic discharge, and increased parasympathetic dominance in the form of significantly decreased heart rate response on standing as well as decreased catecholamine levels in plasma (17).

Fig:4- how yoga helps to reduce the risk of NCDS (15)

Conclusion: Ashtanga yoga can be rationale in preventing and treating patients with non-communicable diseases

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